

(IACS-AMS) Monitoring applications for beneficiaries' compliance checks

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

As in the previous programming period, Member States are required to monitor the compliance of beneficiaries, also considering that new interventions (e.g. eco-schemes) and requirements (e.g. social conditionality) have been introduced. Yet, Member States are now called to **reduce the burden for farmers and the administrative costs** and fostering the simplification of the monitoring systems. IACS systems are in place in all Member States. However, new monitoring applications and technologies are available that could help enhance the monitoring system. The diversity of technologies adopted across the EU represents an **opportunity for peer-learning and replication** of good practices.

MAIN TOOLS ADOPTED: STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Agrisnap (EL)

The tool is a **precision photo app** that allows farmers to send pictures and information about their land parcels to a grant payment body for validation of payments. Through the mobile application, farmers can take geotagged photos of the parcels, which **helps prove the land uses and calculate the aids that will be paid**. The key features offered by the app make the process easier for users.

It facilitates exchanges between agencies and farmers or advisors.

Frequency of updates or improvements could affect accuracy of the tool.

iSIP -Parcel Identification (PT)

The tool is a public access online platform and a technology-based tool. It comprises a database of georeferenced datasets used for **annual checks on agricultural parcels and farming practices**, updating the database, and allowing farmers to confirm or refute collected data. It includes information on **legal constraints, agri-environmental measures, eco-schemes**, and relevant information for rural property management.

It allows updated field information collection, which can be confirmed, rejected and exported by farmers through the app.

The accuracy of data collected depends on the quality of data sources and on the validation by farmers.

BiedjaCam (MT)

The tool streamlines agricultural processes, provides essential information, and **acts as a digital hub for farmers**. It enables instant communication between farmers and agencies, allowing for the submission of geotagged images for evidence-based verification, thereby **reducing the need for physical on-site checks**.

It allows farmers to rectify issues and claim support scheme payments in a timely manner.

It is used only in the monitoring of particular AECCs and Eco-schemes.

